

Acquisition of Digital Marketing Skills and Perceived Employability of Marketing Education Students in Niger Delta University

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Abstract

The research investigated the acquisition of digital marketing skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University. The study was guided by two research objectives, questions, and hypotheses. A descriptive survey research design was employed. The population comprised 123 marketing education students in the Department of Business Education in Niger Delta University. From this population, a sample of 84 students was selected using random sampling technique. Data was collected through a close-ended structured questionnaire titled "Impact of Digital Marketing Skills on the Employability of Marketing Education Students (IDMSEMES)," which demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.82 using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The findings revealed that both male and female students perceive search engine optimization (SEO) and social media marketing (SMM) skills as significantly enhancing their employability. T-test analysis indicated no significant gender differences in the mean responses for both SEO and SMM skills. Based on these findings, it is recommended that Niger Delta University and similar institutions incorporate more comprehensive SEO and SMM training into their marketing education programmes

Keywords: Digital Marketing Skills, Employability, Search Engine Optimization and Social Media Marketing Skill

Introduction

Digital marketing skills are essential for promoting products and services through digital channels. These skills include Search Engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, email marketing, and analytics. Mastery of these skills enhances online visibility and engagement, driving business growth. Chaffey and Smith (2017) highlighted the importance of integrating digital marketing skills into educational curricula to prepare students for the digital economy, thereby improving their employability.

Employability encompasses a set of attributes, skills, and knowledge that enable individuals to secure and retain employment. It includes technical skills, soft skills, and professional behaviours. Yorke (2016) emphasized the need to embed employability skills within academic programmes to ensure graduates are prepared for the workforce, which is crucial when considering the impact of digital marketing skills on employability.

Employment involves engaging in paid work or a profession, marking the transition from education to the professional world. Brown et al. (2018) indicate that employers prioritize candidates with strong digital marketing capabilities, highlighting the importance of these skills in securing employment for marketing education students.

Employability refers to a combination of personal qualities, skills, and knowledge that enable individuals to obtain and maintain employment. This concept encompasses not only the specialized technical skills required for particular job functions but also crucial soft skills, including proficient communication, collaboration, problem-solving, and adaptability. Equally significant are professional behaviours like a strong work ethic, dependability, and the ability to navigate workplace dynamics. Yorke (2016) highlights the necessity of embedding employability skills within academic curricula to ensure graduates are well-equipped for the challenges of today's job market. As the job market continually evolves, the need for employees who can swiftly adapt to new technologies and procedures increases, making employability a vital and dynamic attribute for achieving career success.

In today's rapidly shifting economic landscape, continuous learning and flexibility are vital components of employability. Graduates who can demonstrate a broad set of skills, from technical expertise in their field to effective interpersonal interactions, are more likely to meet the diverse and changing needs of employers. This adaptability not only helps individuals to secure initial employment but also to advance in their careers by taking on new roles and responsibilities as they arise. Employers increasingly value employees who show a willingness to learn and grow, as these individuals can contribute to the organisation's long-term success. Thus, fostering employability through education and training is essential for both individual career development and organisational resilience in the face of market changes (Yorke, 2016).

Marketing education students in Niger Delta University are trained in theoretical and practical marketing knowledge. They face a competitive job market that demands advanced digital skills in addition to traditional marketing expertise. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) argue that marketing education must evolve to include digital marketing components to remain relevant and enhance employability.

Digital marketing skills have a significant impact on the employability of marketing education students, providing a competitive edge in the job market. These skills foster strategic thinking, creativity, and analytical abilities. Taiminen and Karjaluo (2015) assert that integrating digital marketing into educational curricula aligns student competencies with industry needs, enhancing employment prospects with skills such as mastery of search engines, social media marketing and digital marketing skills.

Digital marketing skills cover a wide range of capabilities that enable professionals to effectively market products and services via digital platforms. These skills include, but are not limited to, search engine optimization (SEO), social media marketing (SMM), content creation, data analytics, and email marketing. SEO involves enhancing a website to increase its visibility on search engine results pages, leading to higher organic traffic. SMM is about using social media platforms to interact with audiences and promote brands (Chaffey & Smith, 2017). Content creation is essential for developing engaging and relevant materials that attract and retain customers. Data analytics allows marketers to measure and optimise their digital strategies by interpreting various data points. Email marketing remains a powerful tool for direct communication with customers, fostering loyalty and driving sales.

The growing emphasis on digital marketing skills is highlighted by the worldwide move towards digitalization. Chaffey and Smith (2017) highlight that these skills are vital for enhancing graduates' employment prospects. As businesses across the globe place greater emphasis on their online presence, the demand for professionals adept in digital marketing strategies continues to grow. This trend underscores the critical need for contemporary marketing professionals to possess a robust set of digital marketing skills, which are now fundamental to achieving success in the modern business landscape. As companies strive to remain competitive in an increasingly digital world, the value of digital marketing expertise becomes even more pronounced, making these skills indispensable for anyone pursuing a career in marketing.

Search Engine optimization (SEO) is a crucial digital marketing skill that boosts employability by improving online content visibility in search engine results. Clarke and Rojek (2017) found that SEO skills are highly valued by employers for enhancing an organisation's online presence. Incorporating SEO training into marketing education programmes is vital for student employability.

Clarke and Rojek (2017) explained that search engine optimization (SEO) involves a set of techniques designed to improve a website's ranking on search engine results pages. These techniques are diverse, including keyword research, which entails identifying and focusing on specific terms that prospective customers are likely to use in their searches for products or services. On-page optimization involves refining the content and HTML source code of a webpage to make it more appealing to search engines. Technical SEO focuses on the backend components of a website, such as improving site speed, ensuring mobile compatibility, and facilitating proper indexing, which collectively ensure that search engines can effectively crawl and index the site. Moreover, link building, which involves securing hyperlinks from other websites, is essential for boosting the site's authority and enhancing its search engine rankings.

Employers highly value Search Engine Optimization (SEO) proficiency because it directly influences an organisation's digital presence and effectiveness. Clarke and Rojek (2017) highlighted that strong SEO skills can significantly enhance a company's online performance by attracting organic traffic, which is often more cost-effective and sustainable than paid advertising. Skilled SEO experts can assist companies in attaining better search engine rankings, resulting in enhanced visibility and a greater number of potential customers discovering their services or products. This, in turn, supports business growth and competitiveness in the digital marketplace, making SEO an essential component of any comprehensive digital marketing strategy. The ability to implement effective SEO practices is therefore critical for marketing professionals aiming to drive organic growth and establish a robust online presence for their organisations.

Social media marketing (SMM) enhances employability by using social media platforms to promote products and engage audiences. Felix et al. (2017) highlight the growing demand for SMM skills among employers seeking to leverage social networks for business growth. Mastering SMM can significantly improve marketing education students' employment prospects in the digital age.

Possessing expertise in social media marketing (SMM) is essential for efficiently using social media platforms to promote products, interact with customers, and build brand loyalty. These skills

are becoming increasingly important as businesses strive to harness the expansive reach and interactive capabilities of social networks for their marketing strategies. Felix et al. (2017) underscore the growing demand for proficient SMM skills, which are essential for companies aiming to capitalise on the unique opportunities provided by platforms such as Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram. These skills encompass various activities, including the creation of compelling content, management of online communities, and analysis of engagement metrics. By mastering these areas, marketing professionals can design and implement strategies that not only attract and retain customers but also drive significant sales growth.

Beyond content creation and community management, social media marketing (SMM) competencies encompass a profound comprehension of data analytics and the algorithms governing social media platforms. This proficiency empowers marketers to evaluate the effectiveness of their campaigns, refine strategies grounded in performance metrics, and optimise their content to enhance reach and engagement (Felix et al., 2017). The ability to proficiently navigate and utilise social media platforms is increasingly crucial for marketing professionals, as it reflects the evolving landscape of consumer behaviour and digital communication. As consumers spend more time on social media, their interactions with brands become more dynamic and immediate, necessitating marketers who can respond swiftly and effectively. Consequently, developing strong SMM skills is indispensable for marketing professionals aiming to thrive in today's digital economy.

Integrating digital marketing skills, especially SEO and SMM, into the curriculum of marketing education students at Niger Delta University is essential for enhancing their employability. These skills align student competencies with industry demands, providing a competitive advantage in the job market. As the digital landscape evolves, the importance of digital marketing skills in securing employment will continue to grow.

Statement of the Problem

The global marketplace's rapid digital transformation has significantly altered the skills needed for employability, particularly in marketing. Traditional marketing education often lacks contemporary digital marketing competencies, creating a gap that marketing education students in Niger Delta University and elsewhere must bridge to meet employer expectations and secure jobs in a competitive market. Despite the critical importance of digital marketing skills like Search Engine optimization (SEO) and social media marketing, there is a notable mismatch between what is taught in academic programmes and what employers demand, leading to reduced employability of graduates. This gap means students may be ill-prepared for modern digital marketing roles, affecting their career prospects and professional development. The lack of practical digital marketing training in curricula hinders students' strategic, analytical, and creative skill development, raising concerns about the effectiveness of marketing education in preparing students for today's job market.

In light of this context, the goal of this study is to investigate the acquisition of digital marketing skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the acquisition of digital marketing skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University. Specifically, the study sought to determine the acquisition of:

1. Search Engine Optimization Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University
2. Social Media Marketing Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the Search Engine Optimization skills to acquire and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University?
2. What are the Social Media Marketing skills to acquire and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance

1. **HO₁**. There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female Marketing Education students on the acquisition of Search Engine Optimization Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University.
2. **HO₂**. There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female Marketing Education students on the acquisition of Social Media Marketing Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University

Methodology

This research employed a descriptive survey design. The study was guided by two research objectives, corresponding research questions, and null hypotheses. The target population comprised 123 marketing education students from the Department of Business Education at Niger Delta University. A sample of 84 students was selected from this population using a random sampling method. Data collection was conducted using a close-ended structured questionnaire entitled "Acquisition of Digital Marketing Skills and Perceived Employability of Marketing Education Students (ADMSPMEMES)." The questionnaire underwent a pilot test involving 10 Marketing Education students from the College of Education Sagbama, located outside the study area, administered twice. The instrument demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.82, calculated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). Data analysis was performed using mean ratings, and the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at a significance level of 0.05.

Theoretical Review

The study adopted the Human Capital Theory.

Human Capital Theory, initially proposed by Gary Becker in 1964, underscores the economic benefits of investing in human resources. This theory posits that both individuals and societies can achieve economic growth by enhancing the quality of their workforce through education, training, and healthcare. By improving cognitive abilities and skill sets, education and training increase the productivity and efficiency of workers, which in turn enhances their market value. This concept is particularly relevant in the context of acquiring specialized skills that are in demand in the labor market.

In the modern economy, digital marketing skills such as search engine optimization (SEO) and social media marketing (SMM) are increasingly seen as valuable investments in human capital. For marketing education students at institutions like Niger Delta University, mastering these skills is crucial for their future employability. These competencies not only make students more attractive to potential employers but also equip them with the tools necessary to succeed in a competitive job market. As the demand for digital marketing expertise continues to grow, students who possess these skills are better positioned to secure employment and advance in their careers. The relationship between educational investments in digital marketing skills and employability outcomes can be effectively explained through the lens of Human Capital Theory. By investing in the acquisition of these skills, students enhance their professional capabilities, thereby increasing their chances of finding employment and achieving career growth. This investment in education and training aligns with Becker's theory, which emphasizes the importance of developing human capital to drive economic and individual advancement.

Overall, Human Capital Theory provides a robust framework for understanding how educational investments in specific skills, such as digital marketing, can lead to improved employability for students. By focusing on the development of these competencies, educational institutions can better prepare their students for the demands of the modern workforce, ensuring that they have the skills necessary to thrive in a rapidly changing economic landscape.

Results

Research Question One: What are the Search Engine Optimization skills to acquire and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University?

Table 1.1: Mean and standard deviation analysis of male and female marketing education students on the Acquisition of Search Engine Optimization skills and perceived employability of marketing education students

S/N	Item statement	Male		Female		Total		Remark
		$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\frac{\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2}{2}$	SD	
1	Data Analysis and Reporting skill	3.17	0.89	3.22	0.89	3.20	0.89	Agreed

2	Improving site speed	3.34	0.84	3.24	0.89	3.29	0.87	Agreed
3	Link Building skill	3.23	0.89	3.22	0.85	3.23	0.87	Agreed
4	Ability to create high-quality	3.28	0.90	3.32	0.88	3.30	0.89	Agreed
5	Keyword Research skill	3.28	0.85	3.22	0.98	3.25	0.97	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.26	0.87	3.24	0.90	3.25	0.89	Agreed

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

The data in Table 1.1 reveals that the overall mean score for male marketing education students across all surveyed items is 3.26, which is higher than the cut-off mean score of 2.50, with a standard deviation of 0.87. This indicates that male students endorsed all the items. Likewise, the overall mean score for female marketing education students stands at 3.24, also surpassing the cut-off mean of 2.50, with a standard deviation of 0.90, signifying acceptance of all items by the female students. In summary, the combined grand mean score of 3.25 exceeds the threshold mean score of 2.50, with a standard deviation of 0.89, reflecting a general endorsement of all items by both male and female students.

Research Question Two: What are the Social Media Marketing skills to acquire and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University?

Table 1.2: Mean and standard deviation analysis of male and female Marketing education students on the Acquisition of Social Media Marketing skills and perceived employability of marketing education students

S/N	Item statement	Male		Female		Total		Remark
		$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\frac{\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2}{2}$	SD	
1	Content Creation and Curation	3.30	0.86	3.22	0.89	3.26	0.88	Agreed

2	Analytics and Data Interpretation	3.15	0.93	3.19	0.91	3.17	0.92	Agreed
3	Community Management	3.26	0.90	3.19	0.84	3.23	0.87	Agreed
4	Expertise in creating, managing, and optimizing paid social media campaigns	3.23	0.89	3.16	0.93	3.20	0.91	Agreed
5	Strategic Planning and Execution	3.23	0.84	3.24	0.89	3.24	0.87	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.23	0.88	3.20	0.89	3.22	0.89	Agreed

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

The data presented in Table 1.2 demonstrates that the overall mean score of 3.23 for male marketing education students across all surveyed items surpasses the cut-off mean score of 2.50, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.88. This result implies that all the items received affirmative responses from the male students. Similarly, the overall mean score for female marketing education students stands at 3.20, which is also above the cut-off mean score of 2.50, with a standard deviation of 0.89. This indicates that all the items were accepted by the female students as well. Additionally, the table reveals that the combined grand mean score of 3.22 exceeds the cut-off mean score of 2.50, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.89, signifying that all the items were accepted by both male and female students.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female Marketing Education students on the acquisition of Search Engine Optimization Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University

Table 1.3: t-test analysis on the mean response of male and female marketing education on the acquisition of Search Engine Optimization Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students

Variables	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	t-Cal	Sig	Decision
Male	47	3.26	0.87				
Female	37	3.24	0.90	82	0.11	1.99	NS

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

The t-test analysis indicates that the t-calculated value (0.11) is lower than the t-critical value (1.99) at the 0.05 significance level with 82 degrees of freedom. This finding demonstrates that there is no significant difference in the average responses of male and female marketing education students regarding the impact of search engine optimisation skills on their employability. As a result, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female marketing education students on this issue, is accepted. This outcome suggests that both male and female students equally recognise the importance of SEO skills in enhancing their employability.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean response of male and female Marketing Education students on the acquisition of Social Media Marketing Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students in Niger Delta University

Table 1.4: t-test analysis on the mean response of male and female marketing education on the acquisition of Social Media Marketing Skills and perceived employability of marketing education students

Variables	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	t-Cal	Sig	Decision
Male	47	3.23	0.88				
Female	37	3.20	0.89	82	0.16	1.99	NS

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

The t-test analysis reveals that the t-calculated value (0.16) is lower than the t-critical value (1.99) at the 0.05 significance level with 82 degrees of freedom. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the average responses of male and female marketing education students regarding the impact of social media marketing skills on their employability. As a result, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female marketing education students on this issue, is accepted. This suggests that both male and female students equally recognise the importance of social media marketing skills in enhancing their employability

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study reveal that both male and female marketing education students at Niger Delta University perceive search engine optimization (SEO) skills as significantly enhancing their employability. The t-test analysis, showing no significant difference in mean responses between genders, aligns with studies by Chaffey and Smith (2017) and Clarke and Rojek (2017), which underscore the growing importance and high valuation of SEO skills by employers. The consistent high mean scores suggest a uniform agreement among students on the positive impact of SEO skills, reinforcing the need to integrate comprehensive SEO training into the marketing curriculum to enhance students' job prospects in the digital economy.

Similarly, the impact of social media marketing (SMM) skills on employability shows no significant difference between male and female students' mean responses. This finding aligns with Felix et al. (2017) and Taiminen and Karjaluo (2015), who highlight the critical role of SMM skills in enhancing employability and the necessity of these competencies in digital marketing strategies. The high mean scores and low standard deviations indicate a strong consensus on the importance of SMM skills, underscoring the need for practical SMM training in educational curricula to prepare students for the demands of the digital marketing landscape and improve their employment prospects.

Conclusion

The study concludes that both male and female marketing education students in Niger Delta University perceive search engine optimization (SEO) and social media marketing (SMM) skills as crucial for enhancing their employability. The t-test analysis revealed no significant gender difference in the perceived impact of these skills, underscoring a uniform recognition of their importance. This finding aligns with existing literature, which emphasizes the growing demand for digital marketing competencies in the job market. Integrating comprehensive SEO and SMM training into the marketing curriculum is essential to equip students with the skills required by employers, thereby enhancing their job prospects and preparedness for the digital economy.

Recommendations

It is recommended that Niger Delta University and similar institutions integrate more extensive SEO and SMM training into their marketing education curricula. This integration should include practical, hands-on experience with real-world applications to ensure that students develop the necessary competencies. Collaboration with industry professionals to provide workshops, internships, and guest lectures can further bridge the gap between academic knowledge and practical skills. By doing so, educational institutions will better prepare their graduates for the evolving demands of the digital marketing landscape, ultimately improving their employability and career success.

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